

**FUTURE JOURNEY FOR INDIA IN THE FIELD OF DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION IN
EDUCATION SECTOR**

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Abstract: The Covid-19 pandemic, which has impacted economies across the globe, has also stifled the education sector. By the end of March 2020, the pandemic had spread to over 185 countries and over 95% of all schools, colleges, and universities were closed. Since the epidemic spread so quickly, there were very few plans in place for switching from offline to online instruction, and none could have predicted the potential and threats that such a drastic shift in the industry may present. The result has been drastic, since teachers now anticipate that technology will enable distance learning and teaching. However, post-Covid-19 online learning and education are not the only areas of the education system seeing digital transformation. Indian education, in both urban and rural areas, is still in its infancy. The nationwide lockdown that the government imposed on March 25, 2020, as a result, had a detrimental effect on the educational system. Given that classroom instruction makes up the majority of the Indian educational system, the current situation has made it extremely difficult for educational institutions to operate.

This paper attempts to quantify the extent to which the Covid-19 pandemic unleashed digital transformation in the Indian education sector, outlining some of the important areas of that shift and attempting to provide a roadmap for future e-learning systems. The majority of the secondary sources from which the data came were newspaper articles, periodicals, journals, and different government papers. According to the study's findings, utilizing digital technologies will not only improve educational quality but also have the potential to completely transform the educational experience for both teachers and students in the years to come.

Key words: Online learning, modern education, Covid-19, digitalization, and traditional education.

1. INTRODUCTION

While edtech as a sector has grown tremendously in the past decade, the true impact of its effective application is only now becoming clear. From e-learning platforms, student engagement tools in the classroom, to skill development and continuous learning opportunities for higher education, EdTech has played a significant role in transforming the way knowledge is accessed. In addition to this, the positive government policies and the tech innovations brought about by wide spread internet penetration and the advent of 5G, have further accelerated the transformation of the sector.

There is no doubt that there will be significant educational reforms in 2023 as a result of the new National Education Policy (NEP). STEM-based learning will experience a big push during the next few years as skill-based education picks up speed. In terms of school education, there have been a lot of focused

policy developments that have been designed keeping tech enabled solutions in mind, with the objective of driving digital literacy and inclusiveness in terms of access to quality learning methods. As NEP embarks on its voyage, all school curriculum will experience considerable changes as experiential learning gains popularity. Schools will soon start implementing programs with the primary goal of making learning pleasurable.

After China, India boasts the second largest school system globally. As per the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO), the COVID-19 pandemic impacted 63 million educators across 165 nations. Around the world, 1.3 billion students were unable to attend classes or universities, with 320 million students in India alone being impacted (National Statistical Office, 75th Round, 2017–18). With online instruction and examinations, it has replaced the conventional educational system with one based on educational technologies. The lockdown and shutdown of educational institutions has been announced by the Indian government as a reasonable measure to enforce social separation within communities. During this time, all educational activities such as competitive exams, entrance exams for different universities, school admissions, and exams are held. As the days go by without any. The country's educational system is being severely impacted by the temporary measure of closing schools and colleges in order to contain this outbreak. The way the Indian education system is structured, including its methods for teaching, learning, and assessment, has been significantly impacted. As a result, there has been a trend toward online learning, with a major emphasis on virtual learning to meet predetermined goals and objectives. A lot of stakeholders in education are concerned about the issue of digitalization in the field. ICT skills are becoming more and more important in today's globalized world, particularly in the workplace. As a result, one of the main goals of educational institutions is to prepare future professionals to be able to solve problems and conduct research, with digital proficiency being an essential skill set. The government is currently proposing various policies, programs, and strategies to address educational technology developments in the education sector.

The educational system in India is as diverse as the large nation it inhabits in terms of heritage, language, culture, and other factors. There are schools that emphasize value education by adhering to the Gurukul system, where children are taught under trees despite having access to top-notch infrastructure. There are schools that have fully digitalized, air-conditioned classrooms and transportation. In the meanwhile, there exist institutions that place an emphasis on reading and the kids' physical development through internal activities, while others may afford to participate in international exchange programs. Simultaneously, there are schools where pupils battle for books. India is a significant player in the international education sector. The National Sample Survey Office study states that there are more than 36,000 higher education institutions and more than 1.4 million schools in the nation, serving over 227 million students. India boasts one of the biggest systems of higher learning in the globe. Still, there is a great deal of room for improvement in the educational system.

2. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The evolution of digital technology is regarded as one of the industry's current trends. There is a lot of room for digital change in the Indian educational system, particularly in terms of schools, colleges, and universities.

However, digital methods and digitalization are ways to open access and digitize lecture content. to

instruction or learning materials by making them available online. It encompasses not only new technology but also contemporary working practices. In the field of education, leadership control is just as valuable as technological know-how in terms of rare resources. Prospective students and today's executives must be able to sort through a plethora of digital activities, manage rapidly accelerating innovation cycles, and restructure the business around novel ideas. Modern learners now require a wide usage of digital materials. There is no denying the power of technology. With 1.31 billion people living in the nation, the proportion of technology has significantly expanded in recent years. India, the nation with the second-highest number of social media users and home to almost 140 million mobile phone users, has enormous potential to advance in this area and to appreciate the advantages of technology in the classroom. Prime Minister Modi has launched programs like Digital India, which carry a great deal of responsibility in the field of digital technology. India is to become a knowledge economy and a society empowered by digital means through this. The idea of "Digital India" aims to alter India's educational system. It provides a way to access educational resources on a worldwide scale. In order to increase their knowledge and access a wealth of content online, students these days spend a lot of time on the internet and their smartphones. Universities, colleges, and other educational institutions are forced to adapt these contemporary technologies. Students now have access to a fresh and different platform thanks to the newest technologies.

The Indian education system is gaining fresh hope thanks to the steady growth of technology, the growing popularity of social media, the Internet of Things (IoT), artificial intelligence (AI), augmented reality, and virtual reality.

3. OBJECTIVES

The objective of the study are as follows:

- I. To assess the impact of COVID-19 on the Indian Education System
- II. To research the different opportunities and risks that the educational system may face.
- III. To ascertain India's future outlook for digital education

4. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

4.1. Sources of Data Collection: The study's data was gathered from websites that host current literature and pertinent research publications and periodicals. A number of official reports have also been taken into account.

Study Area: Schools, universities, and other higher education institutions make up the study area chosen for this investigation.

4.2. Study Scope

In India, where there are about a billion people and many of them are online, a wide range of digital tools are being used extensively on a daily basis. There is a great deal of opportunity in the education sector to provide pupils with higher-quality knowledge. At all learning levels, the use of Live and Digital Virtual Classrooms has increased in the upcoming years. Teachers and students will benefit from the flexibility to attend classes at any time and gain superior knowledge by utilizing Open Educational Resources. Simultaneously, in order to have greater responsibility, clarity, and learning engagement,

virtual reality and augmented reality ideas has already begun, enabling pupils to comprehend the idea in practical settings.

5. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Dr. Sumit Sinku (2021) in her research said the Covid-19 pandemic that has affected the world's economies has also muffled the education industry. End of March, 2020 recorded the spread of pandemic to over 185 countries and resulted in closure of over 95% of all schools, colleges and universities. The spread of the epidemic was so speedy and quick that there were hardly any plans for transition to online teaching or learning from offline classes and no one could anticipate the associated possible risks and opportunities that a sudden change could bring in the sector. The effect has been radical, as educators expect technological solutions to support remote education and learning. Digital transformation in education sector is, however, not limited to post Covid-19 online education and learning. Although some educational institutions have used technology solutions for the past years, the importance of digital transformation in education environment has now been realized in most schools, colleges and universities during the pandemic. Indian education system is still not mature at both the urban and rural areas. Under these circumstances government-imposed nation-wide lockdown on March 25th, 2020, has made severe impact on the education system. Since the Indian education system is dominated by classroom study, the present scenario has made the functioning of the educational institutions go very difficult.

Pulkit (2020) explain the current education system in his paper. He wrote India holds a very important place all over the world in education industry. The nation has more than 1.5 million schools with more than 260 million students enrolled and around more than 800 universities and 65,000 colleges. Although, lot of scope for continuous improvement in the education framework. Indian education industry is ready to face significant development in the years to come, as India have world's biggest tertiary-age population and second biggest graduate ability internationally.

Korableva (2019) highlighted on the benefit of online courses over the traditional class room based teaching. In extend of the study, more insight was on the latest two online platforms, MOOC and Course era, to understand which more user convenience is as well as give the best solution in terms of knowledge.

6. CURRENT TRENDS HAVE A BIG IMPACT ON EDUCATION IN 2023

6.1. Augmented reality and virtual reality

Technology is developing, and we have reached a brand-new era when augmented reality (AR) and virtual reality (VR) are quickly gaining traction. Because of virtual reality and augmented reality technologies, children now have a space where they can understand complicated ideas and gain practical learning experiences in low-risk virtual environments. STEM-related classes, simulations of medical procedures, resources in the arts and humanities, technical education, AR, and VR all have the potential to improve it. The capacity to communicate knowledge in novel and more interesting ways online is the second reason why virtual reality and augmented reality technologies are on their way to becoming one of the most promising additions to the "Edtech" field.

6.2. Rise of Real and AI together

Artificial intelligence, also known as AI, can communicate with humans and provide assistance. It has the potential to alter a wide number of sectors, including education, and to solve some of the most pressing challenges facing education today by introducing novel approaches to teaching and learning. The use of AI tools and technology may provide benefits such as faster paper grading, tailored training, intelligent material delivery, and student access to tutoring programs or AI-based intelligent tutoring systems (ITS). Realizing that AI should be centered on people is vital. Giving students a sustainable and high-quality education in the future will be made possible by a mix of teachers' involvement and AI.

6.3. Personalized Education

Personalizing learning for each student's strengths, needs, talents, and interests is yet another straightforward yet very successful and novel approach to the learning process. This aids in creating a learning plan specifically for the learner. The fundamental idea behind introducing customized learning is that every kid learns in a unique way and at a unique speed. Each student in customized learning receives a 'learning plan' based on their learning style, prior knowledge, abilities, and interests. It goes against the 'one size fits all' philosophy that is prevalent in most schools. In order to ensure that the student obtains hands-on learning on the selected topics and that they're expected to learn as they move through their education, the developed plan is kept project-based.

6.4. Holistic learning will be the focus

The emphasis now is on supporting a child's whole and holistic development so they may grow up to be responsible adults with the right skill sets, thanks to shifting educational environments. Educators are increasingly emphasizing the holistic learning approach to education, which emphasizes a child's academic success while also preparing them to confront life's obstacles. There are several advantages to holistic education. Students are given the tools they need to improve their academic achievement as well as develop the soft skills required for a successful professional career. The fact that holistic learning enhances academic achievement, mental and emotional health, and problem-solving skills is only one of its many advantages.

6.5. Education with the Entrepreneurial Mindset

In recent years, there has been a lot of excitement about incorporating entrepreneurship into schooling. Teachers design their lectures and classes to help students develop an entrepreneurial mindset and perspective from an early age. If entrepreneurial ideals are entrenched in the educational process, students will be better equipped to be obedient members of society. Students who are taught such a mindset are better able to acquire the skills and information needed to achieve their own unique goals. As a result, the curriculum designed here aims to build entrepreneurial knowledge, skills, attitudes, behavior, and drive in a way that assures entrepreneurial success while also making the student more employable in the future workforce.

6.6. Key Areas of Digital Transformation in Education

✓ **Online Learning Platforms:** With the widespread use of these platforms, students can now access courses and other instructional materials from internationally recognized educational institutions. This adaptable and self-directed learning style encourages learner autonomy and chances for lifetime learning.

✓ **Virtual Classrooms and Remote Learning:** The creation of virtual classrooms is made possible by digital technologies. removing obstacles related to distance and facilitating distant learning. This becomes especially important in emergency situations where typical classes could not be available, like pandemics or natural catastrophes.

✓ **Gamification and Educational Apps:** By utilizing gamification strategies, mobile applications provide dynamic and captivating educational opportunities. Students can learn in an immersive, individualized environment with educational apps tailored to their ability levels and disciplines.

✓ **Artificial Intelligence (AI) in Education:** AI-powered analytics, flexible learning environments, and intelligent tutoring programs support monitoring student development, spotting areas of knowledge deficiency, and giving customized feedback. Learning results are improved and student engagement is increased by this individualized approach.

7. CHALLENGES IN THE DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION OF EDUCATION

✓ **Networking and Infrastructure.** Inequitable access to high-quality internet connectivity and technology infrastructure is still a major problem, especially in isolated and rural places. For everyone to have fair access to education, closing the digital divide is essential.

✓ **Skills Gap and Digital Literacy:** It is essential to encourage digital literacy among parents, teachers, and students in order to utilizing the capabilities of modern technology. Comprehensive training programs are required to close the skills gap in the use of digital tools and platforms.

✓ **Privacy and Security Issues:** As more people utilize internet resources, it is important to protect kids' data's privacy and security. Establishing strong security safeguards for personal data is essential to fostering trust in digital learning environments.

8. FUTURE DIRECTIONS AND POLICY IMPLICATIONS

In order to effectively capitalize on the advantages of the digital transformation in education, policymakers must develop all-encompassing plans. Infrastructure development, teacher capacity building, and policy creation should be prioritized in order to guarantee fair access to high-quality online education. Innovation in educational technology research and development will be aided by

collaboration between government, business, and academia.

8.1. Prospective Advantages of Digital Revolution in Education

- ✓ **Increased Motivation and Engagement:** Interactive and multimedia-rich learning environments provided by digital tools and platforms grab students' interest and increase their desire to study. Interactive tests, films, and simulations are examples of engaging learning resources that help students get more involved in the process of learning.
- ✓ **Personalized and Adaptive Learning:** Thanks to digital technologies, educational experiences may be tailored to each student's preferences, learning style, and speed. Algorithms and data analytics are used by adaptive learning platforms to provide exams and information that are customized to each student's individual abilities and deficiencies, encouraging independent study and concept mastery.
- ✓ **Data-Driven Decision-Making:** A lot of data about student performance, development, and learning patterns are generated by digital tools. By analyzing this data, educators can gain important insights into the learning trends of their students and use that knowledge to influence decisions about curriculum development, intervention tactics, and instructional strategies.
- ✓ **Teamwork and Worldwide Connectivity:** Teachers and students can collaborate and share information across geographic boundaries with the help of digital platforms. Through the use of video conferencing, online discussion boards, and shared online spaces, students can access knowledge and participate in group projects and cross-cultural interactions from professionals from around the world, encouraging a global viewpoint and improving intercultural understanding.
- ✓ **Prospective Routes and Developing Patterns:** Virtual and Augmented Reality (VR/AR) in Education: By combining VR and AR technology, educators may create immersive and interactive learning environments that let students explore virtual worlds, visualize difficult ideas, and participate in hands-on learning. These technologies have the potential to significantly improve learning outcomes in a variety of fields, including science, medicine, and history.
- ✓ **Blockchain Technology for Credentials and Accreditation:** By enabling safe, tamper-proof verification of academic credentials, blockchain technology ensures authenticity and transparency. By streamlining certification, degree verification, and accreditation procedures, blockchain technology can be used in education to lower administrative costs and boost confidence in credentialing systems.
- ✓ **Big Data Analytics for Educational Research:** By utilizing big data analytics, scholars and decision-makers can uncover patterns, get insights into educational trends, and make well-informed choices to enhance educational practices and policies. Researchers can investigate relationships between several aspects, including student demographics, learning results, and teaching approaches, by analyzing large-scale data.

8.2. Digital Education's Ethical Considerations

Digital Residency and Cybersecurity. In the digital age, it is crucial to teach pupils about responsible digital citizenship and to make sure they are secure online. Digital education programs should include ethical conduct promotion, critical thinking instruction, and instruction on how to use digital spaces in a courteous and safe manner.

Handling Accessibility and Equity: Although digital revolution has enormous promise to improve education, it is essential to address issues of accessibility and equity. In order to close the digital gap, efforts should be undertaken by granting equal access to technological tools, internet connectivity,

and digital resources, especially for isolated locations and underprivileged populations.

Mental Health and Digital Well-Being: It is critical to consider the effects of increasing technological integration on students' mental and physical health. In the context of digital education, it is imperative to address concerns like screen time management and cyberbullying, cultivate digital mindfulness, and encourage a healthy balance between digital and offline activities.

8.3. Government initiatives for Digital Education in India

The Ministry of Electronics and Information Technology (MeitY), Government of India launched the 'Digital India' programme with the vision to transform India into a digitally empowered society and knowledge-based economy by ensuring digital access, digital inclusion, digital empowerment and bridging the digital divide.

To achieve these objectives, particularly in rural, tribal and remote areas, Ministry of Education offers high quality educational programmes through DTH channels as well as web platforms under the aegis of PM e-Vidya.

Some of the major education initiatives are as follows:

- ✓ DIKSHA the nation's digital infrastructure for providing quality e-content for school education in States/UTs and QR coded Energized Textbooks for all grades (one nation, one digital platform). Till date (25.07.2023) DIKSHA has clocked more than 524 crores learning sessions, more than 6,125 crore learning minutes with more than 2.2 crore average daily page hits. A total of 3,17,496 pieces of e-contents are live on DIKSHA as on date.
- ✓ 12 DTH Channels in school education and 22 SWAYAM PRABHA channels in higher education are already functional. As per budget announcement for Financial Year 2022-23, the 12 DTH Channels would be expanded to 200 (Two hundred) PM e-Vidya DTH TV Channels.
- ✓ SWAYAM (Study Webs of Active-Learning for Young Aspiring Minds) is the national MOOC platform with provision of credit transfer to Universities, for Higher Education Courses. NIOS and NCERT are National Coordinator for school sector courses under SWAYAM, delivering school courses from 9th to 12th. On SWAYAM Portal a total of 10,451 Courses are available out of these courses, 257 courses of NCERT and 431 courses of NIOS are available. For NCERT courses 4.1 lakh students are registered and for NIOS courses more than 34 lakh students are registered.

9. CONCLUSION

This study examined the effects of digital transformation on the Indian education system, emphasizing the possible advantages, difficulties, and stakeholder implications. India can establish a more effective, egalitarian, and inclusive education system that equips students for the demands of the digital age by fully utilizing the potential of digital technology. However, in order to guarantee that all students have access to high-quality educational opportunities and succeed in the digital age, it is crucial to address issues with infrastructure, digital literacy, privacy, and equity. The Indian education system can adapt and change over time with cooperative efforts and continued research access cutting-edge technologies, giving pupils the abilities and information need to thrive in the twenty-first century and beyond. The

Indian education system could undergo a revolution thanks to digital transformation, which would increase accessibility, engagement, and effectiveness. Policymakers, educators, and stakeholders can create an education system that is future-ready and equips students to succeed in the quickly evolving digital world by deliberately embracing digital technology and tackling related obstacles. In addition, constant research, cooperation, and adaptability to new trends will guarantee that the advantages of the digital transition are fully realized and that everyone has fair access to high-quality education.

The Indian education system is changing as a result of digital revolution, which presents several chances to improve learning environments and academic results. The main topics of the digital transformation, the difficulties encountered, and the implications for policy are clarified in this study report. India can set the stage for an inclusive education system that is prepared for the future by deliberately adopting digital technologies and tackling related issues.

REFERENCES

- 1) Omer, Oz, (2018), Academicians view on Digital Transformation in Education. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/333354818_Academicians'_views_on_digital_transformation_in_education
- 2) R. Raja, (2018). Impact of modern technology in Education, Journal of Applied and Advanced research, Journal of Applied and Advanced Research, Issue:3, Pp.33-39.
- 3) Vial, G. (2019). Understanding digital transformation: A review and a research agenda. The Journal of Strategic Information Systems.
- 4) Iivari, N., Molin-Juustila, T., and Kinnula, M. (2016). The future digital innovators: Empowering the young generation with digital fabrication and making. Proc. ICIS.
- 5) Papagiannidis, S., Harris, J., and Morton, D. (2020). WHO led the digital transformation of your company? A reflection of IT related challenges during the pandemic. International Journal of Information Management Article 102166.
- 6) Arnab Kundu, Dr. Kedar Nath Dey, (2018). A Contemporary Study on the Flourishing E learning Scenarios in India, IJCRT Journal, Volume 6, Issue 02, https://www.researchgate.net/publication/327671945_A_Contemporary_Study_on_the_Flourishing_E-learning_Scenarios_in_India
- 7) Shirshendu Roy, (2020). e-learning Scope and Trend in India, https://www.researchgate.net/publication/338913710_elearning_Scope_and_Trend_in_India
- 8) Dr. Kapoor Radhika, (2018), Challenges in Indian Higher Education-Indian Context. Research Gate.
- 9) R. Agarwal, G. Gao, and A. K. Jha, (2010) "Research commentary the digital transformation of healthcare: Current status and the road ahead," Information Systems Research, Vol. 21, No. 4, pp. 796-809.
- 10) C. Dede, (2011). "Emerging technologies, ubiquitous learning, and educational transformation," in European Conference on Technology Enhanced Learning. Springer, pp. 1–8.
- 11) N. Cuellar, (2002). "The transition from classroom to online teaching," in Nursing Forum, vol. 37(3). Blackwell Publishing Ltd., pp. 5-12.
- 12) <https://www.indiatodayin.cdn.ampproject.org/v/s/www.indiatoday.in/amp/educationtoday/featurephilia/story/covid-19-impact-digital-education-conventional-education>
- 13) Covid-19 Pandemic in India. Retrieved on https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Education_in_India

- 14) Education in India Retrieved on August 24, 2020 from <https://en.unesco.org/covid19/Educationresponse>
- 15) MHRD notice (20 March, 2020). COVID-19 Stay Safe: Digital Initiatives. Retrieved on May 25, 2020 from <https://www.mohfw.gov.in/pdf/Covid19.pdf>
- 16) Pravat Ku. Jena 2020b. Online learning during lockdown period for covid-19 in India. International Journal of Educational Research, Volume-9, Issue- 5(8), Pp.82-92.
- 17) Tech Financials. (2020). Coronavirus: Overcoming the Educational Digital Divide in South Africa. Accessed 08/08/2020, available from <https://techfinancials.co.za/2020/04/02/coronavirus-overcoming-the-educational-digitaldividein-south-africa/>
- 18) Government of India, Ministry of Statistics and Programme Implementation, National Statistical Office, Key Indicators of Household Social Consumption on Education in India: NSS 75th round, July 2017- June 2018, NSS KI 75/25.2 (New Delhi: National Statistical Office, November 2019), http://www.mospi.gov.in/sites/default/files/publication_reports/KI_Education_75th_Final.pdf
- 19) Mary Meeker, “Internet Trends 2019”, Internet Trends series, Bond Capital, https://www.bondcap.com/pdf/Internet_Trends_2019.pdf
- 20) Dr. Sumita sinku, Digital Transformation In Education Sector: The Way Forward For India JETIR September 2021, Vol 8, Issue1